

REPORT:

A1.1.2: Definitions, Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control.

Work package 1

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1. Scope

This document provides a compilation of basic and general concepts and associated terms related to flow control whose definitions are currently lacking harmonisation. A proposal of definitions and symbols has been produced as well as a Vocabulary of Flow Control (containing terms such as repeatability, stability, settling time, liquid properties, dead volume, volume dispensed, accuracy, range, etc). This compilation is drawn on existing symbols and standards for flow control.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.1.2 M6	Using input from A1.1.1, IPQ, CETIAT, NEL, INESC MN, NQIS, HSG IMIT and BHT will identify basic and general concepts and associated terms related to flow control whose definitions are currently lacking harmonisation. A proposal of definitions and symbols will be produced as well as a Vocabulary of Flow Control (containing terms such as repeatability, stability, settling time, liquid properties, dead volume, volume dispensed, accuracy, range, etc). This compilation will draw on existing symbols and standards for flow control where appropriate.	IPQ , CETIAT, NEL, INESC MN, NQIS, HSG IMIT, BHT

2. Normative References

Normative references for definitions, symbols and vocabulary of flow control can be found in:

- International Organization for Standardization. ISO, International Electrotechnical Commission, IEC, ISO/IEC Guide 99:2007 International vocabulary of metrology — Basic and general concepts and associated terms (VIM) (<https://www.iso.org/standard/45324.html>)
- VIM3: JCGM 200, International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM 3rd edition), BIPM, 2012 (<https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/vim.html>)
- The International System of Units (SI), 8th edition, 2006, updated in 2014, BIPM (<https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/si-brochure>)
- International Organization for Standardization. ISO, International Electrotechnical Commission, IEC, ISO 800000 Quantities and Units; ISO: Geneve, Switzerland, 2020; Parts 1–13
- International Organization for Standardization. ISO, ISO/DIS 10991 Microfluidics — Vocabulary; ISO: Geneve, Switzerland (<https://www.iso.org/standard/82146.html>)

3. Basic definitions

Basic definitions are described in:

- MFMET report *MFMET A2.1.1: Metrology Methodology* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303716>)
- International Organization for Standardization. ISO, ISO/DIS 10991 Microfluidics — Vocabulary; ISO: Geneve, Switzerland (<https://www.iso.org/standard/82146.html>)
- VIM3: JCGM 200, International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM 3rd edition), BIPM, 2012 (<https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/guides/vim.html>)

4. Flow control definitions

4.1. Actuating resolution

Smallest change of a physical parameter that can be actuated by a system that causes a perceptible change in corresponding indication [1].

4.2. Compliance

The increase of a fluidic system's internal volume under the effect of pressure. Expressed in volume units per pressure units, [m^3/Pa], [1].

4.3. Dead volume

The portion of the internal volume of a system that is not part of a continuous flow-path. In this context "dead" signifies unmoving stagnant, or un-swept, [$\mu\text{L}/\text{mm}^3/\text{m}^3$], [1, 2].

In microfluidics the dead volume is the portion of the internal volume that is not part of the flow path. It means that the liquid that enters this area – or the molecules that will diffuse there, may not be recovered, or may be recovered later on. Fluid (and objects or molecules entrained by the fluid flow) particles will stagnate in this volume. It is a kind of "buffer volume". Of course, manufacturers of microfluidic devices try to minimise the dead volumes in their fluidic products. Dead volume can be an issue:

- a) when several samples need to flow through the same path without contaminating one another;
- b) in liquid application as a location for trapping gas bubbles and as an initiation point of clogging;
- c) When the sample volumes to be tested are small.

4.4. Device Stability

Refers to the capacity of the device to maintain a certain physical quantity at a constant value. It is a very important parameter since even small variations in physical quantity during a microfluidic experiment can have dramatic effects on the measurement result. The stability of a microfluidic device contributes to guarantee the repeatability and the reproducibility of the device as well. The stability of a device can be quantified by using statistical measures of dispersion on the sampling recordings, such as the standard deviation of consecutively repeated measurement values [2].

4.5. Flow rate

Quantity of fluid which passes through a given area per unit time. Flow rate can be expressed in mass or volume units per time units [1].

4.6. Flow stability

Standard deviation of the flow rate. Notes: depends on the number of points and time window for which the measurements were carried out. The flow stability of a device can change depending on the application and other parameters fluctuations such as standard stable conditions (e.g. pressure and temperature of the fluid and/or of the ambient conditions) [1].

4.7. Flow Resistance

Fluid movement in microfluidic devices is characterised by low Reynolds numbers and laminar flows where viscous effects prevail compared to inertia. The simplified fluid displacement is thus described by a very simple equation linking the pressure drop, ΔP , applied with the mean flow rate Q the proportionality constant being the microfluidic resistance, R . This equation is also called the Poiseuille (or Hagen-Poiseuille) law [2].

$$\Delta P = R \times Q$$

The flow resistance in microfluidics can be either attributed to the tubing and fittings used to connect the microchip to the flow control system (external flow resistance) or can be related to the design of the microchip itself (internal flow resistance).

The microfluidic resistance, R , for microfluidic channels with cross sections of simple geometrical shapes such as circular or rectangular is directly linked to the channel geometry and the fluid characteristics.

The flow resistance is expressed in pressure units and equivalent to the pressure drop (see 4.17).

4.8. Internal volume

Maximal total available volume comprised within a fluidic component, device or system under normal atmospheric pressure. The internal volume is the sum of the swept and dead volumes, [$\mu\text{L}/\text{mm}^3/\text{m}^3$] [1].

4.9. Fall time

Time required by a system to change from a specified high value (for example 90% of a target or stable value) to a specified low value (for example 10% of a target or stable value) [1].

4.10. Hydrostatic pressure

Hydrostatic pressure is the pressure that is exerted by a fluid at rest at a given height within the fluid, due to the force of gravity. The hydrostatic pressure is expressed in pressure units [1].

4.11. Hydrodynamic resistance

Ratio of pressure drop over flow rate for a certain component or system. Expressed as pressure units over flow rate units [1].

4.12. Latency

The latency is the time interval between the initiation of a sent operation by a source task and the completion of the matching received operation by the target task. More generally, latency is the time delay between the moment an operation is initiated, and the moment it begins to take effect. In microfluidics, latency is the time needed by the microfluidic flow controller to simply react to a given set-point [2].

4.13. Mass flow rate

The mass of fluid which passes through a given area per unit time [1].

4.14. Microfluidic pumps

The handling of liquids in microfluidic devices is accomplished by active components such as microfluidic pumps capable to deliver fluids in a continuous way or in a (discrete) dosing mode.

4.15. Microfluidic valves

Microfluidic valves are used to close or open a flow path, and can be electrically, pneumatic, or mechanically actuated. Usually, microfluidics valves are components used to control the delivery of precise volumes of sample or buffer in the microfluidic device.

4.16. Minimal actuating pressure

Input pressure required to start moving a fluid through the fluidic component. Expressed in pressure units [1].

Note: this refers to components inside the system such as internal membranes, etc., this does not take into account external components.

Note: the minimal actuation pressure should be high enough to overcome the friction forces in the channel.

4.17. Pressure drop

Difference of pressure between two positions in the flow path. Expressed in pressure units [Pa] [1].

4.18. Processing Time

The processing time is the amount of time a system takes to process a given request. It does not include the time it takes the order to get from the user to the system. In microfluidics, processing time is the time needed between the reaction of the microfluidic flow controller and the first move in the setup [2].

4.19. Response time

Interval of time between the set point step change the moment the flow has increased x % of its intended rise or x % of its intended fall. Typically $x = 90$. Expressed in time units [3, 4]. The response

time is the time a system or functional unit takes to react to a given input. It corresponds to the elapsed time between the end of an inquiry on a system and the beginning of a response by the microfluidic flow controller.

Figure 1. Representation of the setpoint of the flow versus time in microfluidics [3]

In microfluidics, response time is the length of time between an indication of the start of flow and the display of the first change in flow at a user's workstation (camera, sensor, monitoring station...). [2]

In these terms: **Latency + Processing Time = Response Time**

4.20. Relative Flow stability

Relative flow stability is also called coefficient of variation. It is the standard deviation of the flow rate divided by the average flow rate. Expressed as a percentage [1].

4.21. Resolution

Smallest change in a quantity being measured that causes a perceptible change in corresponding indication [1].

4.22. Responsiveness

Responsiveness is the ability of an entity to provide service within the required time. Responsiveness thus determines the global ability of a system to reach a setting point. In a microfluidic setup,

responsiveness depends on all the elements of the setup. For example, in the case of pressure controllers' system, responsiveness depends on the volume of air that gets pressurized [2].

4.23. Rise time

The rise time is the time a system takes to change from a specified low value to a specified high value. The rise time is defined as the time required for the response to go from x % to y % of the setting value (Set Point). The 10 % to 90 % rise time is the one most commonly used [2]. The Set Point is the value that should be reached.

In microfluidics, the rise time is the time needed to reach, commonly, from 10 % to 90 % of the setting flow.

Figure 2. Representation of the rising time

4.24. Settling time

Figure 3. Representation of the settling time

The settling time is the time elapsed from the application of some flow to the time at which the flow has entered and remained within a specified error margin of the final value. The settling time includes the response time, plus the rise time and finally, the time needed to be within the specified error margin [2].

In microfluidics, the settling time is commonly defined as the time needed for the response of flow to reach and stay within a certain percentage range, usually 2 % or 5 % of the desired final value (Set Point) of the flow .

4.25. Volume definitions in Microfluidics.

The liquid volume related to and handled by a microfluidic device is defined in several ways depending on the different part of the microfluidic device it occupies. The microfluidic chip has its own volume while the tubing has an internal volume. Fittings, adapters or other components have an enclosed volume that contributes to the total volume of the system. Their volume is referred to as internal volume in the specification of the microfluidic device.

The internal volume consists of two different volumes: the “swept volume” and the “dead volume”.

4.26. Stabilization time

Time after start when the flow reaches the set point and the PID controller takes action. Within this time, after the settling time, the flow does not change significantly [1].

4.27. Swept volume

The swept volume is the portion of the internal volume that is directly in the flow pathway: fluids are bound to flow through this volume when flowing through the fitting. It is generally best to have the swept volume as low as possible, [$\mu\text{L}/\text{mm}^3/\text{m}^3$] [1].

4.28. Sensing resolution

Smallest change in a quantity being sensed that causes a perceptible change in corresponding indication [1]. Can be translated into the standard deviation of the flow rate.

Notes: Needs to take into account the number of points and time window of the measurements carried out.

4.29. Volumetric flow rate

Volume of fluid which passes per unit time. Expressed in volume units per time units [1].

5. Fluid flow control in microfluidics

5.1. Flow generators

Flow rate control is critical for most microfluidic applications and is usually accomplished by external flow generators connected to the microfluidic chip. Four are the most common types used:

- Peristaltic pumps
- Syringe pumps

- Pressure driven flow generator
- Piezo electric pumps

a) Peristaltic pumps

Peristaltic pumps (Figure 4) deliver a pulsated flow. The fluidic tubing used is flexible and coiled around the pump rotor. The rollers on the pump rotor move the fluid by periodically compressing the tubes. The user sets the mean value of the pulsated flow delivered by the instrument by increasing or decreasing the rotation speed expressed in rpm.. The amplitude and frequency of the pulsations depend on the internal diameter of the fluidic tubing, the number of rollers and their rotation speed [4].

The flow rate of such instruments generally ranges from 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to more than 20 mL/min and the typical accuracy of this pumps varies from 1 % to 5 %.

Figure 4. Diagram of a peristaltic pump

b) Syringe Pumps

A disposable or glass syringe is filled with the liquid of interest and is installed on the syringe pump which comprises of a moving motor that is pushing/displacing the piston of the syringe (Figure 5). The motor rotation speed defines the flow rate of the delivered liquid [4].

Typical flow rate ranges from 0.012 nL/min to 1.66 mL/min and the accuracy of this pumps varies from 0.5 % to 2 %.

Figure 5. Diagram of a syringe pump [5]

c) Pressure driven pumps

These devices (Figure 6) control the flow rate by applying pressure to a sealed reservoir connected to the microfluidic circuit. The pressure applied by the air above the surface of the liquid pushes the liquid out of the reservoir into the microfluidic system. A flow meter in the circuit is used as a feedback mechanism to regulate the pressure in the reservoir [4].

Figure 6. Diagram of a microfluidic pressure driven flow generator

d) Piezo electric (or diaphragm/membrane) pumps

Piezo-electric (microdiaphragm) pumps (Figure 7) require compact drives that can provide a continuous flow and variable flow rates. Due to the small volumes per pumping cycle, high cycle rates up to the kHz-range are necessary to achieve high flow rates [6].

A microdiaphragm pump comprises a valve unit and the pump diaphragm, which in conjunction with the piezoelectric actuator forms the pump drive.

The dispensing quantities range from milliliter, microliter, nanoliter right down to the picoliter range.

The fields of application for piezoelectric micropumps are in laboratory technology, medical technology, biotechnology, chemical analytics, and process technology, which require reliable metering of minute amounts of liquids and gases.

Figure 7. Typical schematic of a piezo-electric pump [3]

Other type of pumps can be used in the microfluidic world like electro-osmotic pumps, vacuum pumps and integrated micropumps. Also, a pipette can be used a flow generator, but the generated flow is not controllable or constant due to the manual handling of the pipette.

5.2. Advantages and disadvantages of each type of flow generator

A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of each type of pump are given in the table below.

Table 1 - Summary of flow control characteristics for different types of microfluidics pumps [4]

Flow control characteristics	Peristaltic pump	Syringe pump	Pressure driven pump	Piezo-electric (diaphragm) pump
Flow stability	Low	High	Excellent	High
Response time	High	Low	Excellent	Excellent
Accuracy	Bad	Medium	Excellent	high
Volume limitation (for the liquid to be injected)	None	Yes <i>(depends on the syringe volume)</i>	Depends on the reservoir capacity	None
Fluid recirculation	Possible	Not possible	Possible	Possible
Injection of small volume sample	Bad	Good <i>(use very small volume syringe)</i>	Medium <i>(difficult for less than 1 μl)</i>	Good
Gas injection	No	No	yes	Yes
Sample agitation	Possible <i>(the sample is in a separate reservoir)</i>	Not possible	Possible <i>(the sample is in a separate reservoir)</i>	Not possible
Sample temperature control	Possible <i>(the reservoir can be placed in a thermal bath)</i>	Not possible	Possible <i>(the reservoir can be placed in a thermal bath)</i>	Not possible
Possibility of creating (program) a complex flow profile	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Pressure control	No	No	Yes	No
Flow rate control	Yes <i>(but requires calibration)</i>	Yes <i>(but requires calibration)</i>	Yes <i>(if a flow sensor is added)</i>	Yes <i>(if a flow sensor is added)</i>
High flow rates	Yes	Not suitable <i>(as it is difficult to refill the syringe)</i>	Yes	No

5.3. Symbol for flow generators

The following symbols are used to represent flow generators and its functions [4]:

Figure 5. Symbols suggested for microfluidics pumps

The data sheets found in [4] can be used to define each type of flow generators.

5.4. Flow Sensors

Live flow monitoring can be achieved using flow sensors. An immense variety of flow sensors using different fields of physics are available. Not all of them are suitable for microchannel flows. Choosing the right microfluidic flow meter adapted to the flow regime and fluid is critical for accurate measurements. The next sections will describe some of the main flow measurement technologies.

a) Thermal sensors for flow measurement in microfluidics

A very common technology relies on the calorimetric method. A micro-heater provides a minimal amount of heat to the monitored medium (around 1°C). Two temperature sensors located on both sides of the heater, detect any temperature variation. The flow rate is then calculated based on the spread of heat, which is directly related to the flow rate.

This flow monitoring method is one of the simplest and least intrusive. It is quite easy to build into MEMS devices, since very small heaters and sensors already exist. Nevertheless, it requires knowledge of the fluid density and specific heat capacity. These values also need to be constant for the sensor to operate properly. In biological experiments, the presence of cells or particles in the fluid might influence the fluid properties and impact the measurement.

Several other thermal flow meters exist and operate in a similar way [7]. The hot wire uses a resistor as heater and sensing element. Resistance being dependent on temperature, a relationship between applied tension, temperature and resulting resistance can be established. Other sensors use so-called “time-of-flight sensing”. This technique described in the figure uses only one sensor that is located downstream of the heater. By observing the heat distribution over time, it is able to deduce the fluid velocity and thus the flow rate.

b) Differential pressure flow sensors

There are a number of different flow sensors which work according to the differential pressure method, e.g. Pitot tube, Venturi or orifice plate flow meter. In all cases, the flow velocity is increased by a narrowing of the cross section. This increase leads to a measurable pressure drop in the system, that is proportional to the flow rate. A differential pressure flow meter consists of two main parts: an obstruction or flow resistance that results a pressure drop in the flow path and a transducer before and after to measure the drop.

c) Coriolis mass flow meters

The use of mass flow meters in microfluidics is growing, as the technology is being improved for microscale flows. In a mass flow meter operating using the “Coriolis principle”, the fluid flows in a vibrating channel. The Coriolis force acting on the moving fluid will influence the phase shift and amplitude of the initial vibration proportionally to the mass flow rate. The main advantage of Coriolis mass flow meters is the independence between the measured mass flow rate and the properties of the liquid. Additional feature is the measurement of the density of the liquid in the vibrating channel, since a change in density causes a change in resonance frequency. These sensors can monitor gas or oil flows without any specific calibration. However, the technology remains expensive and the small inner diameter of the fluidic path might not be suitable for biological experiments.

d) Mechanical flow sensor

One of the most important groups of non-thermal flow measurement techniques is mechanical flow sensors. Since flow is usually laminar in microfluidics, laws to calculate the drag force on the channel walls and the pressure drop in the direction of flow are known. Both drag and pressure drop are directly related to flow velocity. By using piezo-resistive transducers or integrated pressure sensors, it is possible to deduce the flow velocity and thus the flow rate in the sensor [8].

e) Other technologies for flow control or flow measurement in microfluidics

Apart from mechanical technology, there are many non-thermal flow measurement solutions available. Some of them involve optics, acoustics or electrochemical phenomena.

5.5. Pressure sensors

Nowadays, pressure sensors are found almost daily in most areas of research and industry, such as the automotive industry, process engineering, medical technology or the chemical industry. They differ in their measuring principle, the measuring range, manufacturing costs and their suitability for specific fields of application. A new but steady growing market for the application of pressure sensors is the field of medical technology.

The most common sensor types are diaphragm-based pressure sensor. Pressure exerted on to one side of the diaphragm results in deflection, whereby the pressure range depends on the diaphragm geometry and properties. The deflection of the sensing element can be measured in several ways e.g. piezoelectric, piezoresistive, capacitive or with strain gauges located on the surface.

5.6. Manual dispensers and Valves

a) Pipettes

Piston pipettes are used to deliver small amount of liquid. These instruments can be of fixed or variable volume. There are also digital pipettes where the delivery velocity can be programmed and its constant. The annual demand of pipettes worldwide is approximately 1 million instruments. There are two types of pipettes the positive displacement or air displacement pipettes, the latest is the most commonly used. The operation scheme is described in figure 7 [9].

Figure 7: Air displacement pipette scheme.

b) Blisters and reservoirs

Many lateral flow assays require the use of a wash buffer, lysis biochemicals, diluent, fluorescence labels, PCR mastermixes etc. The volumes typically range between 5 and 5000 μl . This typically imposes a requirement for a separate buffer bottle and possibly the use of a volumetric or disposable pipette. This can lead to operator error as well as inconvenience and effects on the ability to qualify the device. One alternative is to design features for onboard storage of chemicals

into the system. Integrated unit-dose buffers/reagents can minimize user errors, minimize contamination risks and eases the use. The most simple and reliable form is to have ambient-stable dried reagents in the devices. Alternative options are liquid filled blister packs, pouches or reservoirs. The option to deliver the device with prefilled channels is less often used.

Liquid filled blisters can be manufactured from multiple layers of metal and polymer films with tuned capabilities on chemical resistivity and moisture barriers. The liquid can be release by applying pressure on top of the blister; the foil on the bottom either breaks due to the overpressure or is pushed against a sharp object, puncturing the foil. Technical challenges in implementing blisters include blister design to fit cartridge and reagent volume specification, air free blister filling, reproducible blister rupture, controlled reagent release (volume and rate), and bubble free reagent delivery. The operation scheme is described in figure 7.

Figure 8: a) drawing of the operating scheme of a blister, b) fabricated blister [10]

c) Standalone valves (Piezo valves, SMA valves, MEMS valves, etc)

The market of miniature standalone valves is dominated by solenoid valves, with niche positions for piezo and SMA (shape memory alloy) valves. Most of the miniature valves are designed and used for gases (pneumatic control, medical, processing, etc.). This goes especially for piezo and MEMS (micro electromechanical system) valves. The reason is likely technical: the short stroke. For microfluidic applications one needs strokes exceeding about 100 μm (up to 500 μm). Solenoid valves are inherently bulky and need distance between them to prevent interference: at least 5 mm according to one supplier. Besides, making the solenoid valves smaller will likely make them more expensive, while piezo valves require high voltages which may not be advantageous in explosion sensitive areas. Together with SMA valves, piezo and MEMS valves have the potential of further miniaturization without increasing cost much. Of these three, only SMA valves can offer a pathway towards further miniaturization within the application area of microfluidics; for the others the small actuator stroke is likely a barrier.

Figure 9: DMQ MEMS valve

It must be remarked that a large majority of the microfluidic disposables features a relatively simple flow path, without valves. If a valve is needed, designers mostly use integrated passive valves. Due to the cost of standalone valves, they are used in microfluidics generally in the instruments, not in the disposables.

Interestingly sometimes the valve part and the actuator part are separated: the actuator in the instrument, the valve part on the disposable. In these cases, the top layer of the disposable is a flexible membrane that is pressed by pneumatics or an actuator into the microfluidic channel, blocking the channel. Sometimes we see disposables, also blisters, being operated by actuators in the instrument or manually.

d) Valves mounted on a rail / manifold / microfluidic motherboard

This is the most common method to combine valves. Most of the valve suppliers offer such manifolds. These manifolds can only be used with their own valves. Manifolds are as a rule customer specific. An interesting one among the suppliers is the [Lee Company](#). They specialize in the integration of multiple valves.

Figure 10: Example of a valve manifold from the [Lee Company](#).

Several microfluidic companies also offer manifolds, for instance [Cellix](#). In their ExiGo Manifold a valve is integrated. [Diba](#) also supplies manifolds on demand, likely with valves from their sister company [Bio-Chem Fluidics](#). Many others supply manifolds, generally passive devices without integrated valves, like [Microplumbers](#), [Controlled-Fluidics](#).

Manifolds are seen as offering several advantages compared to just tubing together discrete components, such as fewer leakage points, lower internal volumes, easier assembly into the instrument and higher reliability.

Microfluidic chip holders (Figure 11), offered by several suppliers, are not (yet) supplied with integrated valves.

Figure 11: Example of a chip holder from [Micronit](#)

e) Fully integrated valves

Arrays of pneumatically operated integrated microvalves have been around since the year 2000 in different versions. Each of them involves different advantages and drawbacks but they are all based

on the same principle: the pressure-driven deformation of a soft material (generally silicone or PDMS, polydimethylsiloxane) that clogs or releases liquid flows into microsystems. The method can be used for valving and pumping.

A major advantage of this concept is that it allows for the combination of valves, tubing, pumps and connectors into a single pre-assembled component, thereby reducing production time and costs associated with purchasing, testing, handling and assembling multiple components. Besides that, it allows to integrate a complex processing in a single chip, thereby reducing the usage of expensive chemicals. Additional advantages are a reduction of internal equipment space requirements and elimination of unsightly and unmanageable wiring and tubing.

[Fluidigm](#) licensed their technology from Caltech. Their Nanoflex valves are based on a rubber membrane that deflects under pressure to pinch off the flow of fluids in a microchannel. The valve is made from two separate layers of elastomeric rubber formed in a micro-patterned mold.

Such massive arrays of valves are still rare in microfluidics. This is reflected by the fact that we found this technology offered by only one foundry/design and engineering company: [Aline](#).

A disadvantage of the Quake valves, which are pneumatic valves involving a PDMS bilayer between two microfluidic channels – the flow channel and the actuation channel, is that they need a pressure supply, restricting usage to labs. Additionally, Quake valves need bulky pneumatic controls around the tiny chip. Standalone actuators in the instruments are not an alternative as those valves need minimal distances from each other, restricting miniaturization. That might be different for arrays of SMA valves, with the actuator in the instrument and the fluidic part in the disposable. Still, this is likely a niche product. More opportunities are there for disposables with one or a few valves (and or blisters) in the disposable, operated by actuators in the instrument. An advantage of SMA valves is the miniaturisation.

Other companies have one or more valves integrated in their disposable. They are operated by actuators in the instruments, for example [Biocartis](#).

5.7. Flow control components or accessories

a) Tubing

Typical tube outer dimensions (OD) for side connect devices in microfluidic applications are:

- 1/16" (≈1.6 mm)
- 1/32" (≈0.8 mm)

Do keep in mind that a specific connector usually only supports a single specific tube size.

Smaller sized tubes and capillaries can be beneficial for 1.5 mm pitch side connect applications; preferred tubes outer diameters are:

- 0.5 mm (usually between 0.44-0.53 mm)
- 0.36 mm (usually between 0.35-0.38 mm)

b) Nozzles

Among the different geometries for droplet generation (flow focusing, T-junction, co-flow), the best monodispersity is obtained with flow focusing and co-flow. Generally, they are composed of a nozzle containing the fluid of the dispersed phase embedded in a rectangular or axisymmetric channel containing the shear fluid of the continuous phase. A contraction zone downstream of the nozzle is used in flow focusing devices to change the hydrodynamic behaviour of the flow field and thus the formation of droplets [12].

Figure 12: Schematic concept of exchangeable nozzles within a multifunctional 3D microfluidic device for versatile monodisperse micromaterials production. Sealed connections between the device, tubing, and nozzles enable the on-the-fly exchange of nozzles. This allows for the on-demand switching between nozzles with different diameters, hydrophobicity, absorbance, and complexity. Furthermore, the nozzle placement can be temporally controlled to switch between T-junction, co-flow, and flow-focusing configurations. The multifunctional nature of this microfluidic device enables facile tuning towards the fabrication of emulsions and various micromaterials including microspheres and microfibers [13].

c) Flow generator connectors

The most used connectors in microfluidics are of the following type:

- Luer
- Adaptor to 1/16 or 1/32 tubing
- Needle gauge (20 or 22)

6. Major influences on flow control accuracy

There are several factors that can influence the accuracy and stability in flow control:

6.1. Flow generator

The flow generator should be chosen according to needed accuracy and stability required. It also depends on the application and the microchips characteristics where the flow needs to be imposed.

6.2. Microchips

The obstacles inside the channels cause flow disturbances, pressure losses and internal constraints or even clogging, which will impact the overall flow uncertainty.

6.3. Liquid properties

Several liquid properties affect the flow rate in microfluidic channels, such as viscosity, surface tension and shear stress.

6.4. Leakage

The flow rate can considerably be affected by leakage in the system, often this happens in the connecting points. Leakage can also occur in case of delamination of the chip, or when cracks appear due to overpressure or destructive modification of the chip material (due to over-heat for example).

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